

BIBLICAL PERSPECTIVES ON SANCTITY OF LIFE: EUTHANASIA AND ABORTION FOR NATION BUILDING

BY

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Abstract

This study examined biblical perspectives on sanctity of life through the avoidance of abortion and euthanasia for nation building. Nation building is a major concern in our country today, because when life is preserved it will increase human capital resources which will enhance nation building. God is against killing of any kind even if the person is disabled, sick, very close to death, passing through excruciating pain or through abortion. Historical method was used and the data used were both primary and secondary sources such as observation, books, journals and internet. This paper revealed that the Bible teaches love for one's neighbor and sanctity of life by saying "you shall not kill" (Exod. 20:13 and Rom. 13:9). "He that kills by the sword shall die by the sword". Life is in the blood and innocent blood shed always cry to God for vengeance because blood speaks. Therefore, nobody has the right to take the life of anybody because he or she is not the giver. Only God has the right to take someone's life. The killing of people through euthanasia and abortion is an abomination to God and Man with its consequences. Many people who would have contributed greatly to nation building have died. Therefore, life should be preserved to enhance nation building and endangered human beings who cannot decide for themselves should be protected.

Key words: Euthanasia, Abortion, Nation, Building, Life.

Introduction:

Life is sacred and should be valued, respected and protected. God created man in His image and likeness and asked him to have dominion over everything He had created and commanded him not to kill (Exodus 20:13). God is against killing of any kind, whether through abortion or euthanasia. God has value for human life and has power over it because He is the giver, sustainer and the only one who has the power to determine its beginning and ending.

God opposes killing of any kind, even if the person is fetus, disabled, sick, dying, experiencing excruciating pain, because life is in the blood. It cries vengeance to God. (Genesis 4:10), Abel's blood cried out to God when his brother Cain killed him and God cursed Cain and made him a vagabond on earth. David was denied the building of the temple of God because of the blood he shed in the battlefield (1 Chronicles 22:8) Abraham sacrificed a ram instead of killing Isaac. Therefore, no one has the right to take someone's life.

Methodology:

Historical method was used in this study because it always determines the history of past events in order to understand and interpret current events and predict the future events. This method enabled the researcher to trace the origin of killing in the Bible and how God reacted by cursing Cain and making him a vagabond because he hates killing of human beings. It also helps to understand how Biblical teachings condemned killings of any kind, no matter the condition of the individual. Primary and secondary sources of data collection such as observation, books, Bible, internet and journals were used to gather information for this study.

Definition of Terms**Sanctity of Life**

According to Heike, sanctity of life is the highest respect that human life should be treated with. It is the protection of life, the value of life, and individual rights of all human life beginning at conception. The sanctity of life is the quality of life that makes it so important that it must be respected and preserved, and the quality of life is the level of health, comfort and pleasure in life. Gushee describes the sanctity of life as being sacred, of equal worth and inalienable dignity, at all stages of life, from conception to old age. Therefore, they must be treated with respect, protected and maintained. He went further to state that human life is sacred, because God created it in his own likeness, made it precious, and gave it a unique place in creation. This is why the Bible condemns euthanasia and abortion, because no one has the right to take someone's life because it is sacred and should be preserved.

Euthanasia

Kunhiyop avails that euthanasia is discussion about how to avoid dying and unnecessarily prolonging the dying process. The Bible is against euthanasia. Morris states that euthanasia is the act of killing a person for benevolent reasons. Emeke and Ikegbu posit that euthanasia is the act of causing a person suffering from a disease to die relatively quickly and painless for reasons of mercy.

Abortion

According to Kunhiyop abortion is a deliberate act intended to terminate a pregnancy and kill the developing fetus by removing it from the womb. It is expulsion from the uterus before the fetus is fully developed.

Nation-building

According to Izuegbu, nation-building is the conscious use of people's collective resources, energy and knowledge in the task of liberating and developing a country. It includes the development of behaviors, values, languages, institutions and physical structures that explain our history and culture, protect our present, and ensure the future identity and independence of nations. Aniefiok states that nation-building is concerned with the conscious effort towards unity of a nation, thereby making it stronger. According to Wikipedia, this is a process aimed at uniting people within the state so that the state is politically stable and able to act in the long run. Overall, nation-building has to do with the willingness of people within a state to work together and live together to foster a viable, politically stable community. Nation-building promotes the general cooperation necessary to develop a country's high economic, social, cultural and political status. It is a generally accepted fact that nation-building requires mutual understanding between the people and the leaders. In this sense, leaders are expected to be responsible and accountable to their people. Leaders must respect the functioning and operation of other institutions outside their jurisdiction, and in return, people should do their part to ensure the progress, development and prosperity of the nation.

Sanctity of Life

According to Emeke and Ikegbu, biomedical scientists and researchers have confused the sanctity of life. Because they are looking for something new to solve problems and are free to study all areas of human life. He argued that doctors had no justifiable reason for abortion or euthanasia. Human life is sacred and needs to be preserved no matter how worthless it may appear to human eyes.

Classification of Euthanasia

Emeke and Ikegbu note that euthanasia has been classified into voluntary, involuntary, active and passive euthanasia.

Voluntary Euthanasia

Emeke and Ikegbu postulate that voluntary euthanasia should be permitted on request by a competent person. The BBC writes about "voluntary and involuntary euthanasia" and defines voluntary euthanasia as when the patient wants to die and says so. Refusing treatment or requesting that treatment be stopped or life support machines be turned off. This person may refuse to eat or simply choose death. They

further explained that voluntary euthanasia involves instructing another person to act according to one's wishes. He may be unconscious or brain damaged and unable to speak for himself, or beg for lethal injections, because he is suffering from third degree burns over most of his body. In voluntary euthanasia, the dying person consents to death. An elderly man refuses to go to the hospital because he wants to die at home surrounded by his children. Some scholars who advocate voluntary euthanasia believe that everyone has the right to control their own body and life, so they should be able to decide when, how, and by whom they die. This idea stems from her belief that people should be as free as possible and that unnecessary restrictions on human rights are bad. Christian scholars, who believe in God's sovereignty over creation and the sanctification of human life, disagree because they believe God has the right to decide when a person dies.

Involuntary Euthanasia

Udugwomen states that this type of euthanasia is "a death committed by another person without the consent of the murdered person". In involuntary euthanasia, the decision about death is not made by the person who is about to die. The decision may be made by family, friends, or the doctor himself. In regard to involuntary euthanasia, Immanuel Kant argued that death helps a person who has lost his former dignity through suffering or illness. On the other hand, involuntary euthanasia is never permissible, because no one has the right to interfere with another's will by taking life without permission.

Passive Euthanasia

Gifford stated that passive euthanasia is the death of a patient by removing him or her from an artificial life support system, such as a ventilator or feeding tube, or simply discontinuing the medical procedures necessary to sustain life. This type of euthanasia is commonly known as "letting die". Passive euthanasia is, when you let someone die, the doctor is not directly responsible or involved in ending that person's life, but can be sued for negligence.

Active Euthanasia

According to Emeke and Ikegbu, active euthanasia involves active steps to end the patient's life, usually with the possibility of causing the patient's death by an injection. This means that doctors are performing immediate life-ending actions here, such as administering lethal injections. They further explain that in active euthanasia, the doctor takes action with the intent to cause the patient to die. In passive euthanasia, doctors let the patient die. Since when a doctor causes someone to die, he is performing an action intended to bring about the death of the patient, both passive and active euthanasia have the same result, that is death of the patient, therefore removing a retainer is as murderous as giving a lethal injection.

The Bible's View on Euthanasia

The Bible condemns euthanasia, because euthanasia is one of man's attempts to violate God's authority and sovereignty. Only God has the right to decide when a person should die. Koop states that death is imminent but physicians should not decide when an individual dies. For this reason, under no pretext, in the name of mercy, should one kill or help another to die. Another important fact against euthanasia is the sanctity of human life: Human life is sacred and of great value, regardless of the risk of disease or disability. Human life is precious in the eyes of God and in the fabric of many nations. Euthanasia and assisted suicide therefore devalue human life. Therefore, it must be made known that "death is the opposite of life, but the process of death is part of life", and therefore should not be handled lightly to avoid the wrath of God.

Ozumba avails that it is not all fun, but it's a mixture of pain and joy. We know that pain and suffering are unpleasant for the human body, so he might want to die in the same way he did his job, but as circumstances changed, he became happier. Ecclesiastes 3:2 says there is a time to be born and a time to die.

According to Harris, all forms of euthanasia are homicide, suicide and manslaughter. Therefore, indulging in it in any form is actually immoral. For the following reasons:

1. Euthanasia destroys social respect for life, humiliates humanity, and causes various social grievances. Life has become less valuable, and violent crimes and murders become commonplace.
2. Euthanasia is against the sanctity of human life. Human life is sacred before God because man was made in the image of God (Genesis 1:27). It is therefore wrong to kill any human being for any reason except when found guilty in a court of an offense that demands capital punishment. It is wrong to be associated with any plot, agreement or arrangement to directly or indirectly, take any body's life. God cannot acquit someone who kills another.
3. Euthanasia is suicide or murder. The Bible powerfully declares it "Thou shalt not kill" (Exodus 20:13). When someone chooses to end his own life, he is simply denying God's sovereignty over his life and attacking the sanctity of human life, whether it is involuntary, voluntary, active or passive, euthanasia or assisted suicide. Human life is sacred and should not be taken away from anybody under any circumstance.
4. It is not mercy to kill a patient² Samuel 1:1-16 tells the story of an Amalekite soldier who claimed to have killed Saul in order to save him from an ignominious death at the hands of the Philistine army. He expected honor

and promotion from David for "mercifully killing King Saul", but instead David killed him for killing the Lord's anointed. Killing a malformed infant or a sick adult, or someone very close to death, inflicts the misery of death on that person. On the other hand, if euthanasia should avoid suffering, then killing the patient to avoid suffering is not worth it. Euthanasia is wrong on every level and goes against everyone's desire to live. Choosing death out of frustration, ignorance, and temporary despair does not necessarily mean you have to agree to kill him.

A story of frustration, Elijah narrowly escaped from death, and demanded that God should take his life because he is not better than his ancestors. Then he laid down under a tree and fell asleep. Immediately, an angel touched him and he said: Get up and eat. This period of frustration made Elijah to ask God to kill him but God refused to kill him. Job was similarly afflicted with a disease that would kill him. He was so frustrated that he wanted to die. Even his wife told him that his life wasn't worth it anymore and that he should curse God and end it, but Job didn't. The Bible records that the second half of Job's life was better than the first. This means he shouldn't take his own life as it may not be over with him.

Forman postulates that all humans are created in the image of God, regardless of condition, disease, poverty, or malformation (Gen.2:24). No one can dismiss it as worthless. All life is a gift from God. As Job reminded us when he heard of the death of his children, he is the one who decides when to give and when to take. It is arrogance to decide the end of life. This is not only arrogant, it is forbidden. Economic, social, physical or spiritual reasons are not acceptable valid reasons to end someone's life. Such murder amounts to the murder condemned in the Bible (Exodus 20:13).

We apply the wrong standard when you think that the value of human life can only be measured by its usefulness, happiness, or productivity. Life matters because it exists, not what it produces. Moreover, there is value in suffering and we should not simply try to run away from it. Suffering is to be expected as a consequence of the fall. It will only end when we reach heaven (Rev. 21:4). Through suffering, God teaches us many valuable lessons about himself, the world and ourselves. An individual can learn a lot about loving one another, caring for one another, and relying on God. When the great Apostle Paul was ill, Jesus encouraged him by saying "my grace is sufficient for you" (2 Cor.12:9a).

Although we reject euthanasia, it is also important to recognize that there are times when we must accept the inevitability of death (Hebrews 9:27). Technology cannot completely eliminate death and suffering. After you've done your best to help someone, there's nothing wrong with letting nature take its course. There is no need to go to great lengths to prevent death or prolong suffering. Life ends in death.

Death isn't something we aspire to, but it shouldn't be avoided at all costs. God has set limits for our lives and we must accept them. Part of recognizing such limitation is allowing them to die when the time comes, rather than requiring endless connections to tubes and machines.

Types of Abortion

Kunhiyop is of the view that there are two types of abortion: spontaneous abortion and induced abortion.

Spontaneous Abortion: Is an abortion in which the developing fetus is expelled from the mother's body before it can live outside the womb.

Induced Abortion: Is the deliberate act of terminating a pregnancy and killing the developing fetus by removing it from the womb. Abortion is an evil inflicted on millions of innocent babies and will threaten millions to come. It is a morally unacceptable alternative.

Reasons for Abortion:

According to Lammers and Allen, women have abortions for a variety of reasons. Some people have them because as the pregnancy continues, they are more likely to die because of complications. Others have them because tests have shown that the fetus is physically or mentally handicapped. This study does not discuss the therapeutic reasons for these abortions. Instead, it focuses on abortions that are done solely for parental convenience or in response to societal pressure. A large number of abortions are performed because women cannot bear the social stigma of being unmarried mothers. Pregnancy before marriage is strongly discouraged in many African societies. Pregnant girls can be rejected by their parents and expelled from school, and unmarried women can be fired by their employers. Her desire for an abortion is even greater if she is not interested in children. Even if a couple intends to get married, church marriage policies can lead to abortions. Many mainline and Pentecostal churches always insist that women take a pregnancy test before marriage. If the test is positive, the woman is punished and the wedding is called off. No wonder some people would rather have an abortion than shame themselves or their family. Even a married woman may abort her pregnancy because the baby is a girl and her father refuses to have another daughter. Others feel unable to cope with another child because of poverty, or fear of losing their jobs if they have to take time off due to pregnancy. These women would have used contraception to avoid pregnancy, but did not because of ignorance, misinformation, or simply lack of access to modern contraception. Another reason for aborting a pregnancy is sexual infidelity. If adultery was discovered, her husband could choose to file for divorce and have an abortion rather than having the baby. Abortion is also commonly used to terminate incest pregnancies. Many cultures prohibit sexual

relations between close relatives such as cousins, uncles and nieces, aunts and nephews. When an incestuous pregnancy occurs, the immediate response is to remove the shame through abortion.

Biblical Perspectives on Abortion

Wayne avails that life is in the blood; therefore, whoever has an abortion has killed an innocent soul. The Bible clearly supports the view that life begins at conception, because life is in the blood. Human life is precious and murder is a crime (Genesis 9:6). Of all living creatures, only humans have the ability to relate to God. Only humans have souls made in God's image. (Genesis 1:26). The Bible speaks of God knowing the individual from conception (Jeremiah 1:5). David said he had been guilty since his mother's conception. So, from the time David was conceived, he needed a saviour, Job tells us that God shaped him like clay, shaping his skin, flesh and bones. God created man in his own image. He has a completely different status than other animals. No animal is made in God's image or has a soul. Unique in the order of creation and particularly protected in Scripture, is human life. The basic prohibition and non-justification for killing can be found in Genesis 9:6. Because God created man in His image. "According to the Assemblies of God General Presbytery, all people, including the unborn child, have equal worth and standing before God, as stated in Job's account. For example, they are all the works of his hands "(Job 34:19). God said through Isaiah, "He who formed you in your mother's womb and who helps you, do not be afraid, my servant Jacob" (Isaiah 44:2). Again in Isaiah 44:24 the Lord said: David sums it up like this: You knit me together in my mother's womb. I praise you because I am fearfully and wonderfully made. Your work is great. I know it all too well. When I was created in a secret place, my body was not hidden from you. When I was woven in the depths of the earth, your eyes see my formless body. The Bible recognizes that God has a plan for the unborn child. Only he knows the potential of this child God called Jeremiah to the prophetic ministry. He indicated that the ordination was prenatal by saying: I have made you a prophet of the nations "(Jeremiah 1:5). When the priest Zechariah was ministering at the altar of incense, an angel announced that his wife Elizabeth would give birth to a son named John. It was then revealed that God had a special plan for this child. He was to be the forerunner of Jesus. (Luke 1:11-17).

The Bible recognizes that God is sovereign over everything, including the quality of life of the unborn child. When people reject God, they may easily cheaper human life. Some are considered worth living, while others are considered expendable. According to Wayne who knows whether someone destroyed in the womb might have discovered a cure for cancer? Who knows what blessing millions of children killed before birth might have brought to improve the quality of life, and enhance nation building. People that set themselves up as God to determine if a life is worth living, before or after birth, are usurping the sovereignty of the Creator. There are

things that people do not understand. God's ways are beyond human ways, and God's love is unconditional and takes no account of physical or mental limitations. Therefore, while it may be permissible to use prenatal testing to better meet the needs of the fetus, it is not permissible to use prenatal testing to determine whether the fetus is viable.

Banner opines that the life value of both mother and child is so great that the responsible party must be fined even if neither is fatally or permanently harmed. However, if either the mother or the premature baby is seriously injured or dies, the law applies severe penalties. It is clear that the life of an unborn child is precious, and even unintentionally inflicting injury on the unborn child is a serious crime. God's attitude toward killing innocent people is clear. Death penalty imposed by law (Genesis 9:6; Numbers 35:12), accidental killing in self-defense (Exodus 22:2), or properly hired police and war powers (Romans 13:4, 5). John Calvin, when commenting on Exodus 21:22–23, expressed the horrors of abortion: I still started enjoying it. A person's home is the safest sanctuary, so if killing someone in your own home is more terrifying than killing someone in the field, it would be crueler to destroy an unborn child in the mother's womb before birth. As made by God, children deserve our respect. To destroy an unborn child is to destroy a human being, and to destroy what he or she would have achieved. This point is made clear by God's words to Jeremiah. I have made you a prophet of the nations "(Jeremiah 1:5). Paul makes the same point when speaking of God. 1:15). These great people realized that even in their unborn state, God saw them as fully human.

This truth does not apply only to great leaders. Recognizing that God created both the employer, the employee and the unborn child. Therefore fetus should be regarded as a human being. Any mother of twins will recognize in Genesis 25:21-25 what Rebekah's twin sons experienced when they "pushed one another within themselves." The Lord already knew the fate of these twins. One will be stronger than the other, and the elder will serve the younger. Similarly, in the New Testament, Elizabeth told Mary that as soon as the sound of her greeting reach her ears, the baby in her womb leaped for joy (Luke 1:44). This shows that even unborn children are capable of expressing emotions.

Banner states that fetuses are God's creations and that God shapes their lives. Therefore, we should not take it upon ourselves to end their lives. Instead, people who want abortions should be encouraged to consider other options, such as adoption. We also need to provide material and financial support to people who are forced to have abortions for financial reasons. This assistance should be provided not only at the time of the baby's birth, but also as the child grows. A woman who wishes to have an abortion must also realize that she must harden her heart in order to kill an unborn child, and that what she has done can never be erased from her memory. . There are many testimonies of women who regret killing their babies.

Nor is it easy for a woman to admit to having an abortion. Most Africans believe that the only reason women have abortions is to cover up shameful behavior, and therefore women known to have had abortions are stigmatized. Some infertile women have been accused of having abortions. It is believed that those who have had abortions will find it difficult to have children again. Life is in the blood, says the Bible (Leviticus 17:11) In other words, blood is the source of life, and anyone who aborts an embryo has been killed. For when blood flows, life flows, and no one has the right to kill because he is not the giver of that life. Revelation 13:10 says that he who kills with the sword will die with the sword. One day, the doctor who allegedly aborted many babies woke up and started screaming. I hear the cry of babies, I can't concentrate. They took him to the hospital within five days he died. The blood of the babies he killed cried vengeance to God, and he died (Genesis 4:10). A person who aborts a baby would not be alive if it had been aborted by his mother. Therefore, people should stop abortion to promote nation building.

Conclusion

Nation building is a major concern in our nation today. Shortages of manpower due to euthanasia and abortion have hindered nation-building as many great men and women who would have contributed their quota in nation-building died. Therefore, sustaining life increases human capital resources, which are the strongest for nation-building.

Recommendations

God is the Giver of Life, only Him can decide when to end life. Therefore, the researcher is recommending the following:

1. Life is in the blood and is sacred. Therefore, every human life must be valued, respected, cared for and protected from conception to death.
2. Everyone must be obedient to God and His word by avoiding killing of every kind.
3. Christians should oppose abortion and questionable biomedical research and experiments.
4. Christians should provide biblical moral instruction in their homes, churches and all public spaces.
5. Governments should actively support those who embrace the sanctity of life and go to great lengths to protect the unborn child.
6. We should strive to ensure ethical scrutiny and oppose immoral laws.
7. Christians should advise people with unwanted pregnancies about adoption and other alternatives to abortion, pray and give financial support to

responsible Christian adoption agencies, and love unwanted babies. We need to promote depositing unwanted babies in Christian homes.

8. Christians should compassionately help those who feel remorse or guilt for having performed or participated in abortion or other life-destroying activities by reminding them of the words of Jesus. In John3:37 which says “as many that come to me I will not cast away”
9. Euthanasia and abortion are crimes against God and humanity and should be restricted by governments and non-governmental agencies.
10. Humans are highly valued by God, and life is sacred. That's why we need to protect vulnerable people who can't make their own decisions.

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